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CHRISTIANITY AND POLITICS IN THE PRIMITIVE AND MODERN AGES

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Introduction

Convincingly speaking, it has been discovered that out of about 4,000 Religions existing in the whole Universe, there are three most popular religions: Christianity, Islam, and Judaism. Christianity is the most prominent religion of all because it is the religion that reveals the mind of God to humanity. It is religion that reveals Christ to people and people to God. The agenda of God for humanity is sure and certain. The involvement of Christians in taking a functional and active part in Politics cannot be overemphasized. The plan and purpose of God are for man to fear Him through His teachings and laws. This agenda can only be achieved when Christians take an active part in Politics for a good and formidable government. The main and major objective of this framework is to position us to have the real knowledge and mind of God as His elects. Our responsibilities and assignments in the world of politics as Christians cannot be overemphasized.

"Christianity and Politics in the Primitive Age" is a topic that gives us an understanding and shows the importance of the construction of how Christians participating in politics came into existence. It also reveals the Political Structure that opens ways for cordial relations between Christianity and politics, both in the olden days and in the modern world. The systematic approach and the opportunity given to the Christians to take functional parts in the government, particularly in the Roman Empire, England, America, and so on, are eye-openers. As a result of this, the program of God for humanity to trace back to the right track is His concern. It is imperative to show the world, as children of the most-high God, what we Carry and that we can show forth the glory of God almighty when we are involved and right the wrong. Thus, This

write-up is a serious and fascinating work that focuses on the role of Christianity in Politics in the Primitive Age. The laudable achievements and how Christianity gained prominence politically, especially in the Roman Empire and some other countries, Popular Countries.

Historical background of Christian's involvement in politics

There are numerous thinkers who have come out with the argument that Christianity directly supports a particular political or philosophical position, which is why there have been a wide variety of ways in which thinkers have conceived of the relationship between Christianity and Politics. As a matter of fact, the relationship between Christianity and Politics is a historically complex subject and a frequent source of disagreement in the history of Christianity. On the basis of Christianity and Politics, some thinkers or philosophers also came out to argue for Christian communism, Christian socialism, Christian nationalism, Christian Anarchism, Christian libertarianism, and Christian democracy, respectively.

In the Roman Empire, it was vividly discovered that Christianity was most prominent, and at this period of time, it was very illegal, unacceptable, and an aberration to practice Christianity, the reason being that at that time, those who practiced Christianity were severely persecuted. In 301, the first place where Christianity was officially recognized as a religion was known as the Kingdom of Aiiinemia. During the reign of Constantine the Great, we found out that Christianity gained prominence in Roman Politics at that particular time. In his time, Christianity was given an opportunity by his government, and its practice was also legalized in the Empire in the year 313. Constantine the Great also gave some Christians an opportunity in his government by appointing them to various positions. More so, in 380, Trinitarian Christianity was made the official religion of the Roman Empire. At that period of time, it was officially and generally confirmed that Christians do more and better for the good of the Empire by forming "An army of piety" that prays for the stability of government and the well-being of the Empire and the Emperor. In a nutshell, it has been argued that Christianity made very significant positive contributions to the development of modern democracy.

In the Middle Ages, Christianity took the lead and dominated European politics. Not only that, during the fall of the Western European Empire, the Pope was nominated to effectively serve as the Political leader of the Region. The church, as a body, also maintained a very strong influence over the other kingdoms of Europe. Not only that, but secular rulers also supported the missionaries efforts to expand and enlarge their realms. We equally found out that politics was addressed directly or indirectly in the Bible (Rom 13:1; 1 Peter 2:14–15), encouraging all to follow and obey the authorities of the government as government authorities were instituted by the authority of God.

Denominationally speaking, the Catholic Church is deeply intertwined with the history of European Politics. It developed alongside the status of Christianity as the official religion of the Roman Empire and persisted through the Middle Ages as one of the most powerful political forces in Europe. In 2015, Pope Francis stated that Catholics should be involved in Politics to improve the world.

How should Christians view politics?

As children of God and as Christians, I would like to let us know and keep in mind that there is no political party that is entirely bad as far as politics is concerned; the fact remains that we live in a fallen world. As followers of Christ, what should be our attitudes and our involvement in Politics? It has been said often that "Religion and Politics don't mix." Is that really true? Can we truly have political views outside of the considerations of our Christian Faith? We cannot, of course. The Bible has given us the answers regarding our stance towards Politics and government. Glory be to God! Realistically speaking, God's plans, purposes, and agenda for humanity are already fixed, and His will is inviolable. The truth is that the will of God permeates and supersedes every aspect of life. What He has purposed, He will surely bring to pass; no Government can thwart His will.

My findings and Recommendations

I have come to discover that the relationship between Christianity and Politics is a complex one. I found out that the church has played a mixed role in the history of political liberty, to be sure. At times, it has suppressed Political, religious, and Economic liberty. It is certain and clear that Christianity is not a political program, but it nevertheless gives us a certain way of thinking about the state and the role of politics. As a matter of fact, it is to be noted that a Christian vision of government is clearly different from a secular vision of government with religion sprinkled on top. A Christian vision of government is grounded in key theological and philosophical ideas about the nature of God and reality. The importance of justice and the value of freedom, the role of the family, and a rich understanding of the human person as created in the image of God Made for flourishing and called for an eternal destiny.

Conclusion

I want to conclude by saying, as Christians, let us demonstrate the character of Christ in us in our words, deeds, and actions. We must desist from involving ourselves in the character assassination of those with whom we disagree or using bombastic words or antics laced with hateful undertones. We must extend grace and kindness regardless of political affiliation, religious preferences, or personal behaviors. Let us boldly engage in the political process in an irresponsible and informed manner. Let's remember that it is God Himself who appoints the rulers in all societies. The Bible reminds us that it is He (God) who changes times and seasons; He disposes of kings and raises up another; He gives wisdom to the wise and knowledge to the discerning.

References

Proença, S., Amanda, C., Rodolfo, (2017). *The world first Christian Country?*. "www.bbc.com.

Wilken Robern (1984). *The Christian as the Roman saw it*. Yale University press

Frend ,W. H .C (1968). *The early Church*. SPCK

Richard, J.(1979). *The pope and the papacy in the early middle Ages 476- 752*. (London Routledge& kegan paul) P. 36.

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Ezekiel Adesanmi Omidiji (Ph.D.) attended Nigeria French Village, Adiarra, Badagry, Lagos, and the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, where he bagged his Diploma, Nigeria Certificate in Education, and Bachelor of Arts in Education, respectively. He also proceeded to the Redeemed Christian Bible College in Nigeria, where he obtained a Postgraduate Diploma in Theology. What is more, Dr. Omidiji has a PGD in Management and Administration and a Ph.D. in Theology and Church Planting. He is an ordained minister of God and a former lecturer at the University of Applied Science and Management. He is currently Pastor in Charge of Zone, RCCG, Republic of Benin, and Coordinator of the International Institute of Christian Theologians, Scholars, and Professionals, Republic of Benin Chapter. You can contact him here: **Email: folasanmi042@gmail.com or Phone Number: +22967780726 or +2348034816194.**